

AN OVERVIEW OF *ASTHI SARATA* WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PHYSICAL EFFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda focus on *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Mala* which are the fundamental constituents of human body¹. These three entities are responsible for the maintenance of structural and functional integrity of the body². Among these basic elements. *Dhatu* forms the basic architecture of the body they are meant to accomplish the support and nourishment role inside the body this is completed with the support of *updhatus*. *Dhatus* are especially meant for *dharana*, *poshana* & *utapadan* of *sharer*. *Dhatusarata* is the one of important concept of Ayurved which explains anatomical, physiological as well as cerebral characteristics of eight type of *Dhatusarta*. *sara* defined as *vishudhataro dhatu*. *Vishudhataro dhatu* means the purest, supreme and excellent quality of *dhatu*. The significance of *sara* is to assess the *Bala* of individual. Acharya Charak forward the concept of *Dashavidha Pariksha*. Among *Dashavidha Pariksha*, the concept of *Saara Pariksha*, a vital tool

which reflects the state of Physical, Physiological, Psychological and Spiritual well-being of an individual *Sara pariksha* is a vital tool for assessing person health and knowing prognosis of disease. Examination of *dhatu sarta* is helpful for preventive and restoration aspect, to prescribe appropriate drugs, carrier/occupation guidance.

KEYWORDS: *Dhatu*, *Sarata*, *Asthi Sarata*, *Physical Efficacy*.

INTRODUCTION

Dhatu are the fundamental entities which sustains living body. *Dhatusarata* is the one of prime concept of Ayurved which represents most pure, excellent and strong state of *dhatu*. Such *dhatu* lack any impurities. It is able to perform the various functions with supreme efficiency and endurance. *Asthi Dhatu* is the body's component that remains for a longer time (*Asyate*) and participates in movements (*Kshipyate*) with muscles, placed inside *Mamsa*. It is considered the *Sara* (essence) of the body, as it remains even after the destruction of all other body component. *Sara* which is the essential part or best, considered the purest form of *Dhatu*. Accordingly, *Sarata* of any *Dhatus* it is classified in three classes: *Pravara* (Uttama/highest quality), *Madhyama* (medium Quality) and *Avara* (Heena/ low quality).^[3] Acharya Charak forward the concept of *Dashavidha Pariksha*. Among *Dashavidha Pariksha*, the concept of *Saara Pariksha*, a vital tool which reflects the state of Physical, Physiological, Psychological and Spiritual well-being of an individual. It can be stated that the person who is having good *Sarta* will definitely has a good *Bala*. Acharya Charaka signifies that assessment of *Dhatusarata* is especially beneficial to judge strength of individual. While Acharya Sushruta explained that excellence of *dhatu* is positively associated with longevity and good quality of life. Assessment of *sarta* includes clinical examination of specific organs, physiological activities, reaction to stress, likings etc. We also observe; *sara* or excellent quality *dhatu* are resistant to diseases on contrary *Asara* or poor quality *dhatu* are prone to diseases. Hence more the good quality of *dhatu* in the body more will be strength and immunological status of the body.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To understand and review concept of *Asthi Dhatu Sarata*.
2. To understand and review concept of *Asthi Dhatu Sarata* with special reference to Physical efficacy.
3. To understand and review concept of Physical efficacy.
4. To understand the concept of *Dhatu Sarata*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Materials

Samhitas like *Charak Samhita*, *Susruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Sangraha*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Sharangadhara Samhita*, *Kashyapa Samhita*, Previous works done on concepts under the

study like text books, original research articles, oral presentations, thesis and other published works.

Academic databases like PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, ChatGPT search engines like Google etc.

2. Methods: studying the concepts and reviewing the concepts under study.

Brief review

Dhatusarata: Acharya Chakrapani defines *sara* as *vishudhataro dhatu*. *Vishudhataro dhatu* means the purest, supreme and excellent quality of dhatu.

Characteristics Features of Dhatusarata

The characteristics features of dhatusarata are of two types

A] Murta Lakshana (Pratyaksadarshi)

B] Amurta Lakshana (Anumangamya)

Murta Lakshana (Pratyaksadarshi)

Murta lakshana represents effect of particular dhatusarata on specific organs, its size, shape, situation, appearance, texture etc. Assessment of these characteristic features can be performed by *darshana* and *sparshana pariksha*. e.g. *Rasa sara* individuals are characterized by unctuous, smooth, soft, clear, fine, less numerous, deep rooted and tender hair and lustrous skin.

Amurta Lakshana (Anumangamya)

Amurta lakshana represents effect of particular dhatusarata on nature of individual, his or her psychological status, intellect, behaviour, economical status, health, strength etc. Assessment of these characteristic features is carried out by interrogation method.

e.g. *Rakta sara* individuals are endowed with happiness, wisdom, tenderness, moderate strength and inability to face difficulties.

The Sarata i.e. excellence and strength state of *Asthi Dhatu* in an individual is said to be *Asthi Dhatu Sarata*.

Acharya Charaka has described this *Sarata* in *Vimanasthana 8 Adhyaya* (Verse no. 107).

Acharya Susruta elaborated *Asthi Sarata* in *Sutrasthana 35 Adhyaya* verse no. 18.

Acharya Vagbhata explained *Asthi Sarata* in *Ashtanga Hridaya Sharira Sthana Angavibhaga Sharir Adhyaya*.

Acharya Kashyapa described *Asthi Sara* in *Sutrasthana 28 Adhyaya Lakshanadhyaya*.

A comparative review from all the Acharya's can be explained as follows:

CHARAKA SAMHITA

Asthi Sara Purusha have *Sthoola* (robust), *Paarshnee* (heels), *Gulfa*(ankles), *Janu* (knees), *Aratni* (forearms), *Jatru* (clavicle), *Chibuka* (chin), *Shira* (head), joints of fingers, *Sthoola* (robust) nails and teeth, Other characters of *Asthi Sara*, described by Acharya Charaka are *Mahotsaha* (active and energetic), *Kriyavanta* (induged in works), *Kleshasaha* (can bear pain), *Sara-Sthira-Sharira* (stable and firm body type), *Aayushmanta* (living for a long span). *Sthir sharir* means after being effected by disease, kshaya lakshana are not easily visible.

SUSRUTA SAMHITA

Acharya Susruta in this regard, used the terms *Mahashira-Skanda*. (large head and shoulders), *DridhaDanta-Hanu-Asthi-Nakha* (strong jaw bones, teeth and nails). Acharya Vagbhata in *Ashtanga Hridaya*.

BRIHATA SAMHITA

Physical & External characteristic: These persons are characterized by strong and thick bones.

Physic-Psychological characteristics: They are endowed with strength, knowledge and beauty.

Factors Affecting *Asthisara*

Various factors such as *Ahara* (diet), *Vihara* (lifestyle), *Vaya* (age), etc., impact the status of *Asthi* in the body. Consumption of *Atiruksha Ahara* (dryfood), *Laghu Ahara* (light food), *Avyayama* (lack of exercise) or *Athivyaya* (excessive exercise), *Ati Chankramana* (excessive walking), and *Vridha* (elder age), *Pitrujabhava* influence on the quality of *Asthidhatu*.

Asthi Saara Laksana

Character	<i>Charaka</i>	<i>Susruta</i>	<i>Kasyapa</i>
<i>Sthula Sirastvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Maha Sirastvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Drighu Hanutvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Sthula Chibuktvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Dantatvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Drighu Dantatvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Sthula Jatrutvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Maha Skandatvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Sthula Aratmitvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Janutvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Gulphatvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Parsnitvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Asthitvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Drigha Asthitvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Sthula Parvatvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Sthula Nakhatvam</i>	+	-	-
<i>Drigha Nakhatvam</i>	-	+	-
<i>Mahotsaha</i>	+	-	-
<i>Kriyavantah</i>	+	-	-
<i>Kleshaha</i>	+	-	-

Physical efficacy and Asthi Dhatu Sarta

The *Asthi Dhatu Sarata* which is the excellency of *Asthi Dhatu* involves characteristics like robusticity and heaviness of the bones and joints. Again, these individuals are enthusiastic, active and capable of facing difficulties with strong and firm body with longevity. The physical character mentioned by Acharya Charaka are comparable with strength of bones. *Mahutsahah*, “*Kriyavantah*”, “*Kleshahah*”, all denotes capabilities and endurance, self-efficacy of any person.

We have some modern tools of physical fitness assessment which can help to assess these terminologies. Physical fitness tests, CPET (Cardiopulmonary exercising tests) are some of them. Modified Harvard Step tests can also be utilized to assess the physical fitness. Studies have also been done for assessment of relation between *Dhatusarata* and *Dehabala* with special reference to Harvard step test.^[7] Physical efficiency can be assessed by observing the endurance of persons with the help of Physical Fitness Index (score derived from physical fitness test).

Using this tool, we can effectively assess the cardio respiratory endurance and physical fitness of the individuals with relation to studies of various *Sarata* especially *Asthi Sarata*. The assessment of cardiopulmonary efficiencies and physical fitness indices (PFI) will also help to assess “*Mahotsahah*”, “*Kriyavantah*” “*Kleshahah*” regarding *Asthi Sarata*.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The supreme essence of any *Dhatu* in any human body is termed as *Sarata* of that particular *Dhatu*. The *Sarata* of any *Dhatu* as per ancient *Acharyas* of *Ayurveda*, presents some physical, mental and social characteristics. The *Asthi Sarata* is the supremacy and excellency of *Asthi Dhatu* in an individual.

The *lakshanas* of *Asthisara* can be assessed in three categories: measurement of bony structures, observation (for structures where measurement is not feasible), and interrogation (to assess subjective parameters).

Structures like *Jatru*, *Nakha*, *Danta*, and *Parva*, which are difficult to measure, can be graded as *Pravara*, *Madhyama*, or *Avara* based on observation of proportion and structural integrity. Phycology *lakshana* like *Mahotsaha*, *Kriyavantha*, and *Kleshasaha* can be assessed through effective interaction with the patient regarding their daily activities and physical task performances which represent their physical fitness.

Modern tools of assessment are available nowadays and can be applied to assess these ayurvedic parameters of *Asthi Sarata*. *Asthi Sarata* can be quantified by using battery of tests like Harvard step test, CPET, exercising tests, VO2 Max and calculating PFIs.

Prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders in *Ayurvedic* clinical practice is high and these disorders causes a significant impairment in quality of life. Hence in clinical practice, understanding the state of *Asthi Dhatu* through *Asthisara* facilitate *Ayurveda* physician to have a better prediction on disease progression, potential complications, and the overall resilience of the skeletal system. This enables a more proactive and individualized approach to treatment and enhancing therapeutic outcomes.

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